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**Will Internationalization Influence Foreign investment Performance for China's
Commercial Banks?
——Empirical Evidence from the Four State-Owned Commercial Banks**

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ABSTRACT

The outbreak of the subprime mortgage crisis in 2008 made it necessary for European and American banking giants to shrink their international business to meet the capital needs of the head office, which provided an opportunity for China's commercial banks to develop international business. This study employs the fixed effect model to investigate the relationship between operation internationalization of commercial banks and foreign investment performance, and the dataset herein consists of Bank of China, Agricultural Bank of China, Industrial and Commercial Bank of China and China Construction Bank over the period 2008–2018. The empirical results indicate that the relationship presents a U-shaped curve and the four state-owned commercial banks have spanned over the critical thresholds, so higher degree of internationalization helps in improving the performance of foreign investment.

INTRODUCTION

Commercial banks are regarded as the dominant force in providing financial services and optimizing the allocation of financial resources in financial system. Whether it is the result of continuous marketization or the inherent needs of banks' own transformation and upgrading, commercial banks are actively implementing international business strategies to improve their international market position. In 2008, financial crisis swept the world, and the European and American banking suffered a heavy blow. However, China's banking resisted external risks during the financial turmoil, and achieved substantially improved international competitiveness. The internationalization of commercial banks has gradually become a trend.

Then, will increasing the internationalization of commercial banks help to improve the performance of foreign investment? This issue has attracted much attention with the acceleration of bank's internationalization process. In this case, it is vital how to examine the degree of internationalization of commercial banks and investigate the relationship between internationalization and foreign investment performance. The study provides commercial banks with some advice on how to develop practical international strategies to improve foreign investment performance. Furthermore, the results can provide guidance for other banks to developing international business.

Based on the discussions above, the study takes Bank of China, Agricultural Bank of China, Industrial and Commercial Bank of China and China Construction Bank as samples to investigate the relationship between internationalization and foreign investment performance. The empirical results

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reveal that the relationship presents a U-shaped curve, namely there is a “threshold effect”, and the four state-owned commercial banks have spanned over the critical threshold. In order to further explore the emergence of “threshold effect”, this study also employs the transcendental logarithmic cost function model proposed by Christensen and Jorgenson (1973) to examine economies of scale of the four state-owned commercial banks. The empirical results indicate that the four state-owned commercial banks have achieved economies of scale in international business. Hence, we come to the conclusion: higher degree of internationalization helps in improving the performance of foreign investment.

The main structure of the paper is as follows. Section II examines the existing literature on the relationship between internationalization and foreign investment performance. Section III mainly illustrates the application of fixed effect model and transcendental logarithmic cost function model. Section IV demonstrates the empirical results. Section V puts forward conclusions and suggestions to promote foreign investment performance for China’s banks.

II. Literature Review

Early studies related to the relationship between internationalization of enterprises and foreign investment performance tended to support the linear positive correlation. However, studies in recent years have indicated the relationship may also present an inverted U-shaped curve or U-shaped curve. Moreover, some studies have verified S-curve relationship. In the following section, we will review different scholars' views on this issue.

Some research studies have indicated that the relationship between internationalization of enterprises and foreign investment performance showed linear correlation. Grant (1987) claimed that there is a linear positive correlation between the profitability and the degree of internationalization of British manufacturing companies over the period 1972–1984. Tallman and Li (1996), Delios and Beamish (1999), Berger and DeYoung (2001) also proved Grant’s point of view. Hejazi (2005) revealed that the positive correlation of internationalization with foreign investment performance is more significant for those Canada's banks which are more dominant in the domestic market. However, Collins (1990), Denis (2002) and Jouda et al (2016) argued that higher level of internationalization may lead to lower performance of foreign investment, namely linear negative correlation.

The research results proposed by Geringer (1989), Ramaswam (1995), Hitt (1997) revealed that the relationship curve presented inverted U-shaped by taking manufacturing enterprises as samples. The relationship was significant positive correlation in the early stage of internationalization, while it turned into negative correlation due to rising costs of enterprises in the later period of internationalization. (Gomes and Ramaswamy (1999)). However, some research studies have stated that the relational graphic between them is similar to U-shaped curve (Lu and Beamish(2001), Ruigrok and Wagner(2003), Capar and Kotabe(2003)).

In addition, Contractor et al (2003) proposed a three-stage international expansion theory by studying 11 service industries. In the initial stage of international expansion, the negative relationship between internationalization and foreign investment performance was gradually transformed into a positive relationship (namely U-shaped relationship). In late period, the increase in internationalization was not conducive to the improvement of investment performance, and even a negative relationship between them occurred due to over-expansion (ie, an inverted U-shaped relationship). The above constituted an S-shaped curve. Furthermore, other studies also indicated that the relationship can be S-shaped (Lu (2004), Bae (2008), Outreville (2010), and Chen (2012)).

No consistent conclusion has been attained regarding the relationship. The difference of conclusions comes from three aspects: the determination of the model form, the construction of index system and the inclusion of regulatory variables. It is worth noting that the relationship has been proven to be highly industrial dependent. Therefore, it can be inferred that the relationship between the internationalization of commercial banks and foreign investment performance should be significantly different from the existing research conclusions which come from manufacturing enterprises.

III. Methodology

This study examines the internationalization of the four state-owned commercial banks and investigates the relationship between internationalization and foreign investment performance. In addition, it investigates economies of scale of the four state-owned commercial banks by employing the transcendental logarithmic cost function model proposed by Christensen and Jorgenson (1973).

3.1 Method of Assessing the Internationalization of Commercial Banks

According to the World Investment Report published by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, the internationalization of an enterprise can be measured by the three indicators: the proportion of overseas employees in total employees, the proportion of overseas assets to total assets, and the proportion of overseas turnover to total turnover. In order to comprehensively measure the degree of internationalization, this study uses the transnationality index (TNI) which is the average of the three proportions to assess it.

3.2 The Bidirectional Fixed Effect Model

This study represents the degree of internationalization with transnationality index (TNI) and foreign investment performance with overseas net profit (ONP). By drawing up the curve between TNI and ONP (Appendix 1), it finds that the relationship between the two is nonlinear from 2008 to 2018. When TNI is at a low level, the slope of the curve is small, even negative. That is, internationalization has negative impact on foreign investment performance at this stage. While, the slope is gradually positive with the increase of TNI, and ONP shows a steady growth trend. Therefore, it can be preliminarily concluded that the relationship between internationalization of the four state-owned commercial banks and foreign investment performance is consistent with the U-shaped curve.

In order to determine whether to use a random effect model or a fixed effect model, we test individual random effects and time random effects on sample data by Hausman test. Then, redundant fixed effects test is used to examine time fixed effect and individual fixed effect of sample data. Hence, we employ bidirectional fixed effect model for empirical research. The advantage of this model is that it can clearly reflect the individual difference, and highlight the influence of time and individual factors on the explained variable. The empirical model is as follows:

$$ONP_{i,t} = C_0 + C_1TNI_{i,t} + C_2TNI_{i,t}^2 + C_3GDP_t + C_4EX_t + C_5LnAS_{i,t} + C_6LnNPLR_{i,t} + C_7LnCAR_{i,t} + \alpha_i + \beta_i + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

Here, GDP represents the growth rate of gross domestic product of our country, and EX represents exchange rate of US dollar to RMB. AS, NPLR and CAR represent asset sizes, non-performing loan ratio and capital adequacy ratio respectively as regulatory variables of this model.

3.2 The Transcendental Logarithmic Cost Function Model

Generally, economies of scale of commercial banks is an important factor leading to "threshold effect". Therefore, the study employs the transcendental logarithmic cost function model proposed by Christensen and Jorgenson (1973) to examine economies of scale of commercial banks. We regard the sum of interest expenses, handling expenses, operating expenses and other operating expenses of a commercial bank as the total cost, and take overseas business income as output. What's more, the study regards the number of overseas assets and employees as capital and labor input respectively, and takes them in a logarithmic square form to ensure that they are not subject to elasticity of substitution of factor and elasticity of transformation. The transcendental logarithmic cost function model is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LnTC} = & C_0 + \alpha_1 \text{LnOBI} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_2 (\text{LnOBI})^2 + \beta_1 \text{LnOE} + \frac{1}{2} \beta_2 (\text{LnOE})^2 + \chi_1 \text{LnOA} \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \chi_2 (\text{LnOA})^2 + \gamma_1 \text{LnOBI} \times \text{LnOE} + \gamma_2 \text{LnOBI} \times \text{LnOA} + \gamma_3 \text{LnOE} \times \text{LnOA} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Here, OBI, OE, OA and TC represent overseas business income, overseas employees, overseas assets and total cost respectively. Then, we take the derivative of the function and get the coefficient of scale economy (SCE). The calculation formula of SCE is as follows:

$$SCE = \frac{\partial \text{LnTC}}{\partial \text{LnOBI}} = \alpha_1 + \alpha_2 \text{LnOBI} + \gamma_1 \text{LnOE} + \gamma_2 \text{LnOA} \quad (3)$$

IV. Empirical analysis

A. Data Source and Description of Explanatory and Interpreted Variables

The dataset, obtained from Shanghai Stock Exchange, consists of quarterly data from four state-owned commercial banks for the period 2008 to 2018, and hence totals 168 observations. This study chooses the transnationality index as explanatory variable and overseas net profit as interpreted variable. In addition, the growth rate of gross domestic product, exchange rate of US dollar to RMB, asset sizes, non-performing loan ratio and capital adequacy ratio are regarded as regulatory variables of the model.

B. Empirical Results

Appendix 2 gives the transnationality index data of these commercial banks. The transnationality index of commercial banks is increasing year by year. Bank of China has the highest index among the four commercial banks, and it reached about 20% in 2018. However, the index of large and medium-sized trans-national bank in international market is generally higher than 50% and even it's 80% for Standard Chartered Bank. Hence, the internationalization of the four commercial banks is generally low, and the gap with international advanced banks is large.

Table 1 shows the Hausman tests which indicates that P values of Cross-section random and Period random are minimal, so we can reject the null hypothesis that "model is an individual random effect or time random effect" at 1% confidence level.

Table 1. Hausman Tests

Test Summary	Chi-Sq.Statistic	Chi-Sq.d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	20.345178	1	0.0000
Period random	38.492410	1	0.0000

Similarly, we can reject the null hypothesis that "model is a redundant effect" from the test results in table 2. Therefore, the study employs the bidirectional fixed effect model and the test results of the model are shown in Table 3. The model has a good goodness of fit, and regression coefficients passed the significance test. Furthermore, we can conclude that the relationship between TNI and ONP presents U-shaped curve. Before the inflection point of U-shaped curve, the improvement of internationalization will lead to the decline of foreign investment performance of commercial banks. The necessary condition for internationalization to promote the performance of foreign investment lies in crossing the inflection point of U-shaped curve according to the theory of "unfamiliar burden". In other words, there is a threshold effect in the relationship, and the critical point is one of the emphases for research. The critical value of TNI is as follows:

$$TNI = -\frac{C_1}{2C_2} = -\frac{-2.5083}{2 \times 0.6589} = 1.903\%$$

Table 2. Redundant Fixed Effects Tests

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	115.977504	(3, 123)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	225.545114	3	0.0000
Period F	3.110756	(41, 123)	0.0000
Period Chi-square	119.521607	41	0.0000
Cross-Section/Period F	10.806216	(44, 123)	0.0000
Cross-Section/Period Chi-square	265.809243	44	0.0000

Table 3. Regression Results of Bidirectional Fixed Effect Model

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C_0	-219.2331	59.63364	-3.676332	0.0003
C_1	-2.508254	1.402710	-1.788149	0.0507
C_2	0.658928	0.066826	9.860375	0.0000
C_3	3.598985	1.403416	2.564447	0.0113
C_4	13.40003	3.752887	3.570592	0.0005
C_5	20.18217	3.969801	5.083925	0.0000
C_6	-14.19713	3.329715	-4.263766	0.0000
C_7	-32.92999	9.178973	-3.587546	0.0004
Adjusted R ²				94.47%
F Value			286.368	
Prob (F-statisti)			0.0000	
Cross Section Number			4	
Observation Number			168	

The estimated results of the transcendental logarithmic cost function model in Table 4 show the estimated coefficients of α_1 , α_2 , β_1 , β_2 , χ_1 and γ_2 are significantly different from zero at the 5% level of significance.

Table 4. The Estimated Results of the Transcendental Logarithmic Cost Function Model

	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
α_1	0.628043	0.170319	3.687459	0.0003
$\frac{1}{2}\alpha_2$	0.033858	0.015427	2.194776	0.0296
β_1	-0.485607	0.137137	-3.541032	0.0005
$\frac{1}{2}\beta_2$	0.083099	0.032602	2.548905	0.0118
χ_1	0.248119	0.109348	2.269071	0.0246
$\frac{1}{2}\chi_2$	0.012711	0.014059	0.904094	0.3673
γ_1	-0.092035	0.053016	-1.736000	0.0845
γ_2	-0.049524	0.017611	-2.812162	0.0055
γ_3	-0.004455	0.025672	-0.173523	0.8625
Adjusted R ²	0.8284			
Cross Section Number	4			
Observation Number	168			

Appendix 3 gives the calculation results of coefficients of scale economy (SCE). Obviously, SCEs of the four commercial banks are all less than 1, indicating that the growth rate of business income of these banks is greater than the growth rate of cost. Therefore, the four state-owned commercial banks have economies of scale in their international operations.

C. Discussion

In the above study, we have obtained the critical value (namely 1.903%) of "threshold effect". When the TNI of the four state-owned commercial banks exceeds the threshold value, the foreign investment performance of commercial banks is positively related to the degree of internationalization. From Appendix 2, we can find the TNI of the four state-owned commercial banks is larger than 1.903% in the first half of 2018, and it means the four banks have spanned over the critical thresholds. Although the four banks are still at the initial stage of internationalization, the degree of internationalization has been greatly improved by learning and accumulating international experience to overcome the phenomenon of "paying tuition" in international management. The coefficients of scale economy in Appendix 3 verified the previous conclusion.

V. Conclusion and Countermeasure

A. Conclusion

With the acceleration of world economic cooperation, internationalization and globalization of the bank industry are inevitable trends, with higher risk and profit accompanying them. In addition, the international financial structure has been adjusted in financial crisis and it provided a rare opportunity for China's banks to develop international business. In this case, investigating the relationship between internationalization and foreign investment performance can help to provide commercial banks with some advice on how to develop practical international strategies. In addition, the research results can provide guidance for other banks to developing international business.

We adopt the bidirectional fixed effect model to investigate the relationship between internationalization and foreign investment performance. The dataset used herein, obtained from Shanghai Stock Exchange, consists of quarterly data from Bank of China, Agricultural Bank of China, Industrial and Commercial Bank of China and China Construction Bank for the period 2008–2018, and hence totals 168 observations. Furthermore, the study employs the transcendental logarithmic cost function model proposed by Christensen and Jorgenson (1973) to examine economies of scale of commercial banks. Empirical results indicate that: (1) The relationship between internationalization of commercial banks and foreign investment performance presents a U-shaped curve and the four state-owned commercial banks have spanned over the critical thresholds. Therefore, higher degree of internationalization will help in increasing the foreign investment performance; (2) The coefficients of scale economy (SCEs) of the four state-owned commercial banks are all less than 1, and it means that the international operation of commercial banks has economies of scale.

Although this study only analyzes the four state-owned commercial banks, the approach herein can also be used to investigate other banks in our country. It is worth noting that the “critical value” of commercial banks' international operations is in dynamic changes. The “critical value” calculated in this paper can only be used to analyze whether the foreign investment performance of the four banks is in a growing trend, and should not be used as a direct standard to examine the foreign investment performance of other banks.

B. Countermeasure

Here, we will put forward some countermeasures and suggestions on improving the degree of internationalization of commercial banks to increase the foreign investment performance.

(1) The commercial banks should make financial innovation by taking advantage of their own business advantages to diversify overseas income structure. More concretely, Bank of China can apply the advantages of foreign exchange business to bank cards, financing, agency and settlement to meet the diverse needs of customers in different countries. Agricultural Bank of China can focus on agriculture and farmers as key targets, and innovate agricultural financial products to develop microfinance services for farmers to help agricultural diplomacy between China and other countries. The core competitiveness of Industrial and Commercial Bank of China is electronic banking, so the cross-border e-commerce payment system which integrates the functions of foreign exchange sale, payment collection and balance of payments declaration should be improved to provide all-round financial services for overseas e-commerce transactions. China Construction Bank can make use of its core competitiveness in infrastructure financing and real estate finance to focus on infrastructure project evaluation, cost consultation and financial advisory services and vigorously develop asset securitization business to increase overseas revenue.

(2) The commercial banks should establish a strong business relationship with new quality customers of other countries such as central bank, super-sovereign institutions and sovereign funds to promote internationalization of banks. The RMB is given the status of reserve currency as it is included in the special drawing rights, and the motive power to absorb the RMB is triggered. In this case, the commercial banks should make use of business advantages and product innovation to develop distinctive financial services to increase overseas institutional customers.

(3) Introducing international shareholders to improve governance structure of commercial banks and increase the capital adequacy ratio of Banks. Introducing foreign capital will help to broaden capital supplementary channels and make the capital supplementary mechanism more flexible. It is beneficial to enhance the ability to raise long-term stable funds overseas and achieve a balance between overseas assets and liabilities in terms of scale and duration. Furthermore, introducing international shareholders is conducive to the introduction of advanced foreign management experience and technical means to accelerate integration with international practices in cross-border operations and improve the profitability of overseas assets.

(4) Pay close attention to the non-performing loan ratio of commercial banks and strengthen internal control over the cross-border credit risk of banks. Commercial banks should establish cross-border risk identification and assessment system for overseas branches referring to the risk assessment system and risk assessment method of foreign banks from parent banks. More concretely, banks must strictly implement pre-lending investigations, loan review and post-lending inspections, and attach great importance to the daily monitoring of cross-border credit risk, and carry out risk warning and crisis management. On the other hand, overseas branches should establish a “firewall” mechanism in corporate governance structure that is independent of the parent bank, and maintain relative independence in terms of risk management, business decisions and related transactions.

Appendix 1

See Figure 1.

Figure 1 the relationship curve between TNI and ONP

Appendix 2

See Table 5.

Table 5. The Transnationality Index of the Four State-owned Commercial Banks

	ABC	ICBC	CCB	BOC	Average
June 2008	0.28%	2.28%	1.53%	18.31%	4.92%
December 2008	0.39%	2.29%	1.35%	18.43%	4.76%
June 2009	0.45%	2.34%	1.34%	16.68%	4.66%

December 2009	0.52%	2.63%	1.75%	17.83%	5.27%
June 2010	0.54%	2.54%	1.49%	16.49%	4.81%
December 2010	0.70%	2.84%	2.04%	17.78%	5.40%
June 2011	0.83%	3.10%	1.78%	17.54%	5.37%
December 2011	0.77%	3.61%	1.54%	16.22%	5.14%
June 2012	1.04%	3.75%	2.05%	16.42%	5.40%
December 2012	1.35%	4.74%	2.02%	16.41%	5.73%
June 2013	2.01%	5.00%	2.25%	16.21%	5.96%
December 2013	2.10%	5.18%	2.48%	17.95%	6.47%
June 2014	2.49%	5.86%	2.59%	19.11%	7.10%
December 2014	1.90%	5.89%	3.01%	19.05%	7.01%
June 2015	2.76%	6.94%	3.19%	19.26%	7.57%
December 2015	3.00%	6.64%	3.18%	17.50%	7.21%
June 2016	3.25%	9.82%	3.38%	21.34%	9.09%
December 2016	3.16%	8.89%	3.60%	18.74%	8.17%
June 2017	5.08%	11.01%	4.59%	19.82%	9.82%
December 2017	3.36%	9.96%	3.61%	20.43%	8.76%
June 2018	4.43%	9.81%	3.39%	19.15%	8.59%

Appendix 3

See Table 6.

Table 6. The Coefficient of Scale Economy of the Four State-owned Commercial Banks

	ABC	ICBC	CCB	BOC
First quarter of 2008	0.1570	0.1475	0.1015	0.0401
Second quarter of 2008	0.1093	0.1448	0.1161	0.0607
Third quarter of 2008	0.0962	0.1454	0.1219	0.0725
Fourth quarter of 2008	0.0956	0.1482	0.1191	0.0757
First quarter of 2009	0.1101	0.1579	0.0992	0.0668
Second quarter of 2009	0.1116	0.1519	0.1003	0.0591
Third quarter of 2009	0.1108	0.1402	0.1238	0.0470
Fourth quarter of 2009	0.0982	0.1343	0.1184	0.0470
First quarter of 2010	0.0602	0.1152	0.0889	0.0579
Second quarter of 2010	0.0679	0.1244	0.0822	0.0622
Third quarter of 2010	0.1158	0.1538	0.0924	0.0618
Fourth quarter of 2010	0.1088	0.1457	0.0857	0.0660
First quarter of 2011	0.0665	0.1135	0.0688	0.0775
Second quarter of 2011	0.0512	0.0777	0.0583	0.0748
Third quarter of 2011	0.0435	0.0456	0.0494	0.0520
Fourth quarter of 2011	0.0462	0.0531	0.0440	0.0437
First quarter of 2012	0.0555	0.0513	0.0445	0.0496
Second quarter of 2012	0.0543	0.0666	0.0359	0.0505

Third quarter of 2012	0.0335	0.0768	0.0149	0.0519
Fourth quarter of 2012	0.0579	0.0792	0.0193	0.0514
First quarter of 2013	0.1012	0.0708	0.0476	0.0482
Second quarter of 2013	0.1040	0.0726	0.0480	0.0487
Third quarter of 2013	0.0881	0.0859	0.0248	0.0527
Fourth quarter of 2013	0.0802	0.0822	0.0241	0.0534
First quarter of 2014	0.0795	0.0601	0.0396	0.0515
Second quarter of 2014	0.0650	0.0550	0.0404	0.0521
Third quarter of 2014	0.0018	0.0598	0.0318	0.0555
Fourth quarter of 2014	0.0024	0.0603	0.0308	0.0559
First quarter of 2015	0.0483	0.0631	0.0362	0.0527
Second quarter of 2015	0.0520	0.0599	0.0305	0.0550
Third quarter of 2015	0.0396	0.0482	0.0092	0.0717
Fourth quarter of 2015	0.0421	0.0459	0.0089	0.0592
First quarter of 2016	0.0505	0.0489	0.0183	0.0339
Second quarter of 2016	0.0637	0.0562	0.0312	0.0027
Third quarter of 2016	0.0601	0.0278	0.0727	0.1060
Fourth quarter of 2016	0.0030	0.0180	0.0510	0.1000
First quarter of 2017	0.0349	0.0109	0.0376	0.0953
Second quarter of 2017	0.0358	0.0066	0.0325	0.0921
Third quarter of 2017	0.0222	0.0051	0.0398	0.0894
Fourth quarter of 2017	0.0277	0.0061	0.0430	0.0905
First quarter of 2018	0.0085	0.0098	0.0463	0.0944
Second quarter of 2018	0.0354	0.0161	0.0496	0.1012

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